

An Inventory Decision Policy Where the Customer's Demand Depends on Price and The Wide Variety of Mortgage Installments that Serve Low-Capacity Consumers¹

Robin Singh

Department of Mathematics, Graphic era Hill University, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India
robinsingh@gehu.ac.in

Sandeep Kumar

Department of Mathematics, Graphic era Hill University, Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India
drsk79@gmail.com

Mangal Singh Bisht

Department ASHD, GBPIET Ghurdauri Pauri Garhwal, Uttarakhand, India

Prachi Fartyal

Department of Mathematics, Govt PG College, Bazpur (US Nagar), Uttarakhand, India
prachifartyal@gmail.com

Abstract

Monetary competency is one of the key drivers for shoppers to make pay for. Consequently, sellers have to set a premier promoting price and keep in mind alternate credit score centers to draw extra demand. This paper proposes a stock selection model in which patron call for depends at the charge and quantity of credit score part payments to set out low-abled shoppers. Current work presents a demand characteristic with a good effect on installment guidelines and the impact of the promoting charge. Two policies have been presented to minimize the promoting fee and advantageous goods time, m total earnings, with and with- out part time payment rules. Two numerical examples are given, and their sensitivity evaluation illustrates the presented version for special cases. The study shows that the promoting price and advantageous stock time may be optimized. profits may be better within the case of an installment facility than inside the case without an installment facility. It indicates nice responses from the consumer to the installment coverage.

¹Address Author Correspondence to Mangal Singh Bisht at drbishtms@gmail.com

Accepted: 29 November 2023 / Published online: 05 December 2023

© The Author(s), 2023. Paper ID, 100320.

Keywords

Inventory, Installment, Demand, Low-Capacity Customers.

1. Introduction and Literature Review

In commercial enterprises, it's vital to lure extra consumers to purchase goods. Sellers provide a rebate on the promoting charge, make sure assurance, and sell merchandise to attract service with fix quantity of down price. It's going to promote the low-abled shoppers reimburse only partial payment of the initial purchase rate after which whole the fee in several installments [1]. The promoting fee of a services or products is a critical thing that affects shopper's purchase purpose. So, dealers have to choose the top-quality rate to certify an income and entice the purchaser. The impact of fee at the EOQ version has been formulated and reviewed within the demand function [8, 9, 10]. Different authors blended the charge and different elements including stock degree [11, 12], promoting attempt [13, 14], and time for decaying items [15]. Many researchers have tested the subject of high purchases with the aid of imparting a discount at the selling charge, ensuring warranty, promoting merchandise, and many others., but studies focus on low-abled customers' flow were a charming area of working in today's time. In this current work we discuss a brand new EOQ model providing an installment service to compel the products cheap for clients. in addition, you'll discover the high-quality impact of the installment on the client's call for. The installment service impresses the purchaser's interest in purchasing products, i.e., selling the enterprise [16]. Then again, customers with limited financial sources would possibly take advantage of this installment service to purchase their merchandise [17]. In this method, the foremost endowments of the present version are as follows:

- (i). We present an EOQ policy including charge and credit score installments-related call for. The study can stimulate patron demand even as helping financially poor clients via supplying installment schemes with a low charge.
- (ii). The proposed version optimizes the promotion charge and tremendous inventory stock time to make sure that the vendor maximizes the full income. An answer set of rules is formulated for this purpose.
- (iii). Two illustrations are discussed, with and without installment service.

The benefit of a late payment is that the consumer needs to charge lots capital to buy goods and might make the most of promoting them to different clients in the permissible delay duration special with the aid of providers. Furthermore, the dealer can observe this settlement as an income enhanced technique to draw new purchasers and encourage new items in the market. Installment service inside or out of the allowed put off period is a technique for stock control problems.

In study [2] authors discussed installments inside the approved delay time, and in article [3] researchers discussed model below the traditional financial request quantity model's suppositions, acquiring diverse consequences. Inside the equal way, in look at [4] mentioned the alternate-credit period with protection era to lessen deterioration. Further to the amount of the low fee and the length of the commendation time, the range of partial payment is likewise an element, because it orders the full funds, the consumer must set apart for each fee. Here, in current work an economic order amount (EOQ) version is introduced that imparting partial payment service, and it results on the rate of demand. partial payment

service has two blessings to the trader: (1) it entices extra shoppers who are weak financially, and (2) can be taken into consideration as an option to the provider of fee rebate as it neither elicits rate reducing from competition nor does it determine everlasting charge discounts. The effect of postponing payment on customer call for price attracted [5], [6] and [7]. The work became primarily related to the fact that exchange credit will boost consumers' buy quantity because of extra assets and entice new clients. but the studies handiest inspected the duration of late intervals.

In study [20] authors presented the policy (EOQ) with a rate-structured demand fee, that is extra unique. Some authors have taken into consideration demand as fee related in a unique pattern [19, 20, 21]. In study [12] authors explored such an inventory version wherein call for is rate and inventory-dependent demand is also taken as function of charge, time/commercial, and commercial [13, 14]. Consequently, call for is dependent on diverse marketplace factors as addressed by look at [22]. Consequently, the work on stock control with variable demand is non-stop inside the identical pattern. This work considers the changeable demand way to give up it well suitable for innate commercial enterprise situation. The customers are thinking about the charge of an item earlier than creating a buy. So, our look has covered the impact of price on call for.

In this way, the EOQ model is being revised temporarily. Several works have elaborated the flexibility of clearance to attract the purchaser. Authors in study [2] analyzed an EOQ policy with allowed delay in payment. The issues of "late payment, as an inducement policy, in the EPQ and EQQ policies" were analyzed in [23]. According to study [24], late payment can be categorized into 4 kinds depending on the payment period. According [25] authors built an inventory policy with a trade credit scheme where demand is inflation related. In study [11] authors used permissible late payments in a policy where the demand is related to price and stock and price although in study [26] authors elaborated various periods of trade credit with the EOQ model including shortages. Article [28] considered late payments in their study and checked the customers interest of buying. Again, in article [29] authors presented a study for defective items with shortages and trade credit. Researchers in [30] modified it with trade credit policies by choosing investment in preservation technology. Authors in [9] included trade credit and price-related requirement with completely backlogged shortages in an EOQ policy. Currently, authors in [17] stated the EOQ policy with late payment by granting various installments after order shipment. For the time being, study [16] discussed various buying nature of the buyers when the vender provided installment payment services. Therefore, late payment with installments is an interesting research area in inventory control techniques. To our best information, this is the first addition of the effect of partial payment in demand for inventory studies. Therefore, we included relaxation in payment for adjusting the number of installments among buyers and sellers and within a complete restock cycle in our present work.

In this method, the EOQ version is being modified in the interim. Several research have addressed the flexibility of payment to draw consumers. Authors in have a look at [2] stated an EOQ scheme with an allowed price postpone. The problems of late in payment, as a provocation gadget, inside the inventory models" had been elaborated in [23]. Authors examined in [24], late payment can be categorized into four sorts relying on the duration of price. According [25] authors constructed a stock version with an exchange credit score policy wherein call for is inflation prompted. Authors [11] applied permissible put

off in bills in a stock model wherein call for is stock and rate-established, whereas in look at [24] authors mentioned extraordinary change credit score periods with the EOQ model for permitting shortages. Article [28] protected put off in payments and consumer return coverage to draw clients. once more, the EOQ model with shortages, trade credit and investigation for imperfect products concurrently appeared in article [29]. Researchers in [30] presented a policy with the aid of thinking about preservation technology funding. Authors in [9] authors included exchange credit and fee-touchy demand in an EOQ model with backlogged shortages. These days, authors in [17] elaborated the EOQ policy with put off in payment with the aid of allowing multiple installments after order shipping. Meanwhile, look at [16] authors identified one of a kind buy conduct of the clients while the vender provided installment fee offerings. Consequently, late payment with installments is an interesting study place in stock control. in keeping with our great know-how, that is the primary merging of the effect of installment in demand for EOQ inventory presented. Therefore, we inscribed price relaxation for placing the quantity of installments amongst dealers and shoppers within a complete replenishment cycle in our gift study. Imparting fee rebate is another inventory control method to impress more extra customers. Numerous research on EOQ stock models often uses this technique. In study [31] and [32] researchers elaborated an EOQ policy with a charge bargain facility for decaying products.

Authors in [33] presented a scheme with discount in quantity and in [34] blended reductions and defective portions with EOQ. Greater currently, in examine [10] authors added the rate dis- remember effect on call for, however the rebate isn't always griping to financially weak clients. By thinking about the troubles of financially poor clients, there's a chance to introduce different schemes to serve them. This technique elaborates the installment policy to assure greater clients for buying the products instead of providing charge reductions.

The inventory deficiency is a notable comfort for mitigating the demand of buyer. In work [35] authors considered shortages, trade credit and later policy to include the vender's ordering determinations. Authors in [27] also considered late payments inwhich shortages are backlogged partially. Authors in [36] analyzed an EOQ policy with the rebate service and problem of shortages which are partially backlogged. Still the problem of the shortages is a great interest of the research. Overall, we presented our model under shortages which are partially backlogged. This work elaborates an EOQ policy with partially backloging shortages where the demand depends on installment and price. With the discussed literature review, it is obvious that our present work idea has never been analyzed.

The inventory scarcity is a good-sized mission for mitigating the consumer's call for. In [35] authors included shortages, later coverage, and trade credit score to consider the store's requirement choices. Authors in [27] also included permissible postpone payments where scarcity is partial backloging. Authors in [38] studied an EOQ version with the bargain service and brief age undertaking, that's backlogged partially. The task of the dearth of merchandise continues to be within the research hobby. in the other components of this work the assumptions and notations are provided. In keeping with the belief and its solutions, the mathematical model system is formulated and followed through the set of rules for solution processes. The numerical outcomes of the troubles and the sensitivity analysis are offered respectively. A dialogue of the results is supplied and, ultimately, the realization with future

scopes of research is provided.

2. Notations and Assumptions

2.1 Notations

First, notations for outlining the mathematical version and the assumptions for describing the environment of the proposed model are provided on this phase. Notations used for the duration of the paper are given below.

n	: Count of installments
H	: Per unit holding cost
P	: Per unit purchase cost
L	: Per unit cost due to decrement in sales
α	: Area Parameter
β	: Coefficient of selling price
r	: Rate of interest
Q	: Total sold quantity
A	: Down payment amount
V	: Quantity of shortages
M	: Per cycle maximum stock level
s	: Selling price.
t_s	: Positive stock time
$TP(s, t_s)$	: Total profit

2.2 Assumptions

In present study following assumptions are made

- (1). Supplier's replenishment rate is infinite.
- (2). Lead time is zero like [1] and [14].
- (3). To examine the impact of installment on the consumer's call for, there are instances as follows:

Case I: EOQ policy with installment service where rate of interest must be charged.

Case II: EOQ policy without installment service

- (4). The demand for a single product is taken into consideration. The demand rate is as follows:

$$D(s, n) = \begin{cases} \alpha - \beta s + \mu A \\ \alpha - \beta s \end{cases}, \text{ where } \mu = {}^{n-1} C_n$$

- (5). Shortages are permitted for this adaptation and are backlogged partially with the rate of

$$G(t) = \frac{1}{1 + \delta(T - t)}$$

Where δ lies between 0 and 1, it is known as backloging parameter.

(6). No effect of inflation and deterioration on the costs

3. Formulation of The Model

The warehouse stocks are at a maximum M at $t = 0$. The inventory decreases because of demand during $[0, t_s]$ and will be zero at $t = t_s$. A shortage V is there at the time $[t_s, T]$ as market demand is not fulfilled after $t = t_s$. The complete procedure might be replenished within the subsequent cycle.

Therefore, the stock machine described via the end resulting differential equations and considering call for $G = \alpha - \beta s + \mu A$ are

$$\frac{dI(t)}{dt} = \begin{cases} -G, & 0 \leq t \leq t_s \\ \frac{-G}{1 + \delta(T-t)}, & 0 \leq t \leq T \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dI(t)}{dt} = \begin{cases} I_1(t), & 0 \leq t \leq t_s \\ I_2(t), & 0 \leq t \leq T \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

With conditions $I_1(t) = M$ at $t = 0, I_1(t) = I_2(t) = 0$
 at $t = t_s$ and $I_2(t) = -V$

Solutions of (1) and (2) are as follows.

$$I_1(t) = -Gt + Gt_s \quad (3)$$

$$I_2(t) = \frac{G}{\delta} \log \{1 + \delta(T-t)\} - \frac{G}{\delta} \log \{1 + \delta(T-t_s)\} \quad (4)$$

Shortages $V = \frac{G}{\delta} \log \{1 + \delta(T-t_s)\}$

and maximum stock

$$M = Gt_s$$

3.1 Sales Income

The income from sales depends on purchaser demand, quick- age, hobby, promoting charge, and high-quality stocks. The following mathematical formulation calculates the sales for our association.

$$SI = \int_0^{t_s} Gdt + Vs + r(M + V)(s - A)$$

$$= \left[s \left(\frac{s\mu}{2} s\beta + \alpha \right) \left\{ \delta(T - t_s) + \frac{1}{2} \delta^2 (T - t_s)^2 \right\} + s \left(\frac{s\delta}{2} - s\beta + \alpha \right) t_s \right] \quad (5)$$

3.2 Inventory Costs

Inventory holding cost, the ordering cost, lost sale cost and purchase cost are calculated as follows: Each replenishment cycle wishes to rate some because of processing the order from the dealer, termed as order value (OC). Our inventory machine considers OC to be constant. After receiving the ordered inventories at the warehouse, they may be held earlier than getting offered out. this period from receiving to depleted/bought is the maintaining period for each inventory. During this retaining period, to control the goods at the warehouse, a value named protecting value (HC) arises. If H is the consistent with-unit preserving value for inventories $I_1(t)$, then the full conserving price is calculated by means of the subsequent formula.

$$HC = H \int_{t_s}^T I_1(t) dt = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{s\mu}{2} - s\beta + \alpha \right) H t_s^2 \quad (6)$$

Because of shortages, shops will lose some opportunities to promote. This loss is named misplaced sale price (LC), that's derived from the following system:

$$LC = L \int_{t_s}^T D(1 - G(t)) dt = L \left(\frac{s\mu}{2} - s\beta \right) \left[T + \frac{(T - t_s) + (T - t_s)^2 \delta^2}{\delta} - t_s \right] \quad (7)$$

The value because of buy merchandise is called the purchase cost (laptop). recall the unit purchase cost is P then the whole purchase cost is:

$$PC = P(V + M) \quad (8)$$

3.3 Profit

Total inventory profit Z can be determined by excluding all costs from the total sales income, i.e., Z = sales income— holding cost – ordering cost – purchase cost- -cost due to lost sale.

Then $Z = SI - HC - OC - PC - CL$

With installment coverage, clients will not pay the whole cost of products when they purchase them. customers most effectively pay the down price, and the relaxation can be paid through the installment method. This installment coverage lets in affording a steeply priced product with much less expense. Consequently, low-abled clients may also be able to buy a product that is no longer low priced to them without an installment facility. in this way, the seller can cowl greater clients inside the marketplace. the full income according to cycle is:

$$TP_1(s, t_s) = Z / T = \frac{1}{T} [SI - HC - OC - PC - CL]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left[s \left(\frac{s\mu}{2} s\beta + \alpha \right) \left\{ \delta(T - t_s) + \frac{1}{2} \delta^2 (T - t_s)^2 \right\} + s \left(\frac{s\delta}{2} - s\beta + \alpha \right) t_s \right] \\
 &- \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{s\mu}{2} - s\beta + \alpha \right) H t_s^2 - P(V + M) \\
 &- L \left(\frac{s\mu}{2} - s\beta \right) \left[T + \frac{(T - t_s) + (T - t_s)^2 \delta^2}{\delta} - t_s \right]
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

4. Results

In this part, two numerical examples are taken to verify the current model.

Example 1: (With installment policy) Assume the holding cost per unit $H=\$2$, purchase cost per unit $P=\$8$, , lost sale cost $L=\$7$, order cost $OC=\$120$, cycle length $T = 4$ months, number of installments $n = 6$, rate of interest $r =\$0.12$ and the values of parameters are $\alpha =240$, $\beta =10$, $\delta =0.6$.

Example 2: (Without installment policy) Consider the same values as in example 1 except few $n = 2$, $s = A$, i.e., the customer can pay for the product one time only and $r = 0$.

In both the examples our aim is to find Our objective is to find the optimum values of TP_1 , Q , s and t_s .

Table-1

Example	Optimal Results			
	Q^*	s^*	t_s^*	$TP_{1,*}$
1	235.28	18.98	2.68	726.34
2	218.45	18.14	2.57	717.46

Table 1 suggests that the entire bought amount and profit are better for the case of installment facility than without installment facility though the charge is better for the first one.

5. Conclusion

In a competitive enterprise marketplace, all retailers and buyers seek to facilitate more consumers to growth their income. Therefore, the provider executes a couple of regulations to draw greater clients. some clients are not able to buy merchandise for cash fee whilst it's far beyond their monetary ability. As a result, this observation considers installment coverage for individuals who are not able to pay the price at a time. We include a call for characteristics that are based on the promoting fee and the range of installments. This looks at mixed the EOQ inventory policy with the part-time payment service and in partially backlogged shortages. The presented set of rules can resolve the version by maximizing the selling rate and nice inventory time. Here two cases have been analyzed and it became located that greater buyers should buy with the installment alternative compared to the whole fee scheme. The

outcome illustrates that the part time payment plan is relative to the total earnings. Installment service-related demand results in a great effect on the demand of buyers. Eventually, this study efficiently elaborates how the installment service can facilitate the poor buyers in the market. Further studies may be extended to using exceptional call for patterns inclusive of inventory-established demand, time-based demand, promoting-structured demand, and providing a reduction on increase price where shortages may be absolutely backlogged for the identical situation. Moreover, sustainable inventory control that includes environmental and social criteria may be analyzed in the usage of the proposed model inside the modern-day study. The impact of inflation can also be incorporated, and a study of multi-merchandise will give more guidelines for managers.

References

1. A.H.M. Mashud, M.R. Hasan, Y. Daryanto, H.M. Wee. "A resilient hybrid payment supply chain inventory model for post COVID-19 recovery." *Computers and Industrial Engineering*, vol. 157, 107249, 2021. DOI: 10.1016/j.cie.2021.107249
2. S.K. Goyal. "Economic order quantity under conditions of permissible delay in payments." *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, vol. 36, pp. 335-338, 1985. DOI: 10.2307/2582421
3. S. Chand, J. Ward. "A note on economic order quantity under conditions of permissible delay in payments." *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, vol. 38, pp. 83-84, 1987. DOI: 10.1057/jors.1987.10
4. A.H.M. Mashud, M.R. Hasan, Y. Daryanto, H.M. Wee. "Non-instantaneous deteriorating inventory model under the joined effect of trade-credit, preservation technology and advertisement policy." *Kybernetes*, vol. 49, no. 6, 1645-1674, 2020. DOI: 10.1108/K-05-2019-0357
5. J. Heydari, M. Rastegar, C.H. Glock. "A two-level delay in payments contract for supply chain coordination: The case of credit-dependent demand." *International Journal of Production Economics*, vol. 191, pp. 26-36, 2017. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijpe.2017.05.004
6. B. Marchi, S. Zanoni, M.Y. Jaber. "Credit-dependent demand in a vendor-buyer model with a two-level delay- in-payments contract under a consignment-stock policy agreement." *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, vol. 99, pp.585-605, 2021. DOI: 10.1016/j.apm.2021.07.002
7. G. Bi, P. Wang, D. Wang, Y. Yin. "Optimal credit period and ordering policy with credit-dependent demand under two-level trade credit." *International Journal of Production Economics*, vol. 242, 108311, 2021. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijpe.2021.108311
8. H. Polatoglu, I. Sahin. "Optimal procurement policies under price dependent demand." *International Journal of Production Economics*, vol. 65, no. 2, pp. 141-171, 2000. DOI: 10.1016/S0925-5273(98)00240-0
9. A.H.M. Mashud. "An EOQ deteriorating inventory model with different types of demand and fully backlogged shortages." *International Journal of Logistic Systems & Management*, vol. 36, pp. 16-45, 2020. DOI: 10.1504/IJLSM.2020.10016452
10. M.R. Hasan, A.H.M. Mashud, Y. Daryanto, H.M. Wee. "A non-instantaneous inventory model of agricultural products considering deteriorating impacts and pricing policies." *Kybernetes*, vol.

- 50, no. 8, 2264-2288, 2021. DOI:10.1108/K-05-2020-0288
11. S. Pal, G.S. Mahapatra, G.P. Samanta. "An inventory model of price and stock dependent demand rate with deterioration under inflation and delay in payment." *International Journal of System Assurance Engineering and Management*, vol, 5, pp. 591-601, 2014. DOI: 10.1007/s13198-013-0209-y
 12. V. Pando, L.A. San-José, J. Sicilia, D. Alcaide-López-de- Pablo. "Maximization of the return on inventory management expense in a system with price – and stock- dependent demand rate." *Computers and Operations Research*, vol. 127, 105134, 2021. DOI: 10.1016/j.cor.2020.105134
 13. M.R. Hasan, A.H.M. Mashud. "An economic order quantity model for decaying products with the frequency of advertisement, selling price and continuous time dependent demand under partially backlogged shortage." *International Journal of Supply and Operations Management*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 296-314, 2019. DOI: 10.22034/2019.4.2
 14. L.A. San-José, J. Sicilia, B. Abdul-Jalbar. "Optimal policy for an inventory system with demand dependent on price, time and frequency of advertisement." *Computers and Operations Research*, vol. 128, 105169, 2021. DOI: 10.1016/j.cor.2020.105169
 15. R. Maihmi, I. Nakhai-Kamalabadi. "Joint pricing and inventory control for non-instantaneous deteriorating items with partial backlogging and time and price dependent demand." *International Journal of Production Economics*, vol. 136, pp. 116-122, 2011. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijpe.2011.09.020
 16. L. Wang, J. Tian, W. Si, X. Sun. "Optimal duration, rate and price when online retailers offer installment payment services." *Nankai Business Review International*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 96-121, 2021. DOI: 10.1108/NBRI-08-2019-0039
 17. P.K. Ghosh, A.K. Manna, J.K. Dey, S. Kar. "An EOQ model with backordering for perishable items under multiple advanced and delayed payments policies." *Journal of Management Analytics*, 2021.
 18. V. Kim, H. Huang, S.W. Shinn. "An optimal credit policy to increase supplier's profits with price-dependent demand functions." *Production Planning and Control*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 45-50, 1995. DOI: 10.1080/09537289508930252
 19. J.G. Szmerekovsky, V. Tilson, J. Zhang. "Analytical model of adoption of item level RFID in a two-echelon supply chain with shelf-space and price-dependent demand." *Decision Support System*, vol. 51, no. 4, pp. 833-841, 2011. DOI: 10.1016/j.dss.2c011.02.002
 20. A.K. Sahoo, S.K. Indrajitsingha, P.N. Samanta, U.K. Misra. "Selling price dependent demand with allowable shortages model under partially backlogged-deteriorating items." *International Journal of Applied and Computational Mathematics*, vol. 5, 104, 2019 DOI: 10.1007/s40819-019-0670-7
 21. M. Pour-Massahian-Tafti, M. Godichaud, L. Amodeo. "Disassembly EOQ models with price-sensitive demands." *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, vol. 88, pp. 810-826, 2020. DOI: 10.1016/j.apm.2020.06.011
 22. R.M. van Steenbergen, M.R.K. Mes. "Forecasting demand profiles of new products." *Decision*

- Support System*, 139, 113401, 2020. DOI: 10.1016/j.dss.2020.113401
23. C.H. Glock, E.H. Grosse, J.M. Ries. "The lot sizing problem: a tertiary study." *International Journal of Production Economics*, vol. 155, pp. 39-51, 2014. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijpe.2013.12.009
 24. Z. Molamohamadi, M. Rezaeiahari, N. Ismail. "Consignment inventory: review and critique of literature." *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*, vol. 3, no. 6, pp. 707-714, 2013.
 25. D. Jain, K.K. Aggarwal. "The effect of inflation-induced demand and trade credit on ordering policy of exponentially deteriorating and imperfect quality items." *International Transactions in Operation Research*, vol. 19, no. 6, pp. 863-889, 2012. DOI: 10.1111/j.1475-3995.2012.00849.x
 26. C.K. Jaggi, V.S.S. Yadavalli, M. Verma, A. Sharma. "An EOQ model with allowable shortage under trade credit in different scenario." *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, vol. 252, pp. 541-55, 2015. DOI: 10.1016/j.amc.2014.12.040
 27. K.V. Geetha, R. Uthayakumar. "Economic design of an inventory policy for non-instantaneous deteriorating items under permissible delay in payments." *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics*, vol. 223, pp. 2492-2505, 2010. DOI: 10.1016/j.cam.2009.10.031
 28. M. Ghoreishi, G.W. Weber, A. Mirzazadeh. "An inventory model for non-instantaneous deteriorating items with partial backlogging, permissible delay in payments, inflation- and selling price-dependent demand and customer returns." *Annals of Operational Research*, vol. 226, pp. 221-238, 2015
 29. Y. Zhou, C. Chen, C. Li, Y. Zhong. "A synergic economic order quantity model with trade credit, shortages, imperfect quality and inspection errors." *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, vol. 40, no. 2, pp. 1012-1028, 2016. DOI: 10.1016/j.apm.2015.06.020
 30. D.J. Mohanty, R.S. Kumar, A. Goswami. "Trade-credit modeling for deteriorating item inventory system with preservation technology under random planning horizon." *Sādhanā*, vol. 43, 45, 2018. DOI: 10.1007/s12046-0180807-0
 31. S. Makoena, A. Olufemi. "Economic order quantity model for growing items with incremental quantity discounts." *Journal of Industrial Engineering International*, vol. 15, pp. 545-556, 2019. DOI: 10.1007/s40092-019-0311-0
 32. M.R. Hasan, Y. Daryanto, T.C. Roy, Y. Feng. "Inventory management with online payment and preorder discounts." *Industrial Management and Data System*, vol. 120, pp. 2001-2023, 2020. DOI: 10.1108/IMDS-05-2020-0314
 33. H.K. Alfares, A.M. Ghaithan. "Inventory and pricing model with price-dependent demand, time-varying holding cost, and quantity discounts." *Computers and Industrial Engineering*, vol. 94, pp. 170-177, 2016. DOI: 10.1016/j.cie.2016.02.009
 34. T.Y. Lin. "An economic order quantity with imperfect quality and quantity discounts." *Applied Mathematical Modelling*, vol. 34, pp. 3158-3165, 2010. DOI: 10.1016/j.apm.2010.02.004
 35. Z. Molamohamadi, R. Arshizadeh, N. Ismail, A. Azizi. "An economic order quantity model with completely backordering and nondecreasing demand under two-level trade credit." *Advances in Decision Sciences*, 340135, 2014. DOI: 10.1155/2014/340135
 36. A.A. Shaikh, M.A. Khan, G.C. Panda, I. Konstantaras. "Price discount facility in an EOQ model

for deteriorating items with stock-dependent demand and partial backlogging.” *International Transactions in Operational Research*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 1365-1395, 2019. DOI: 10.1111/itor.1263

